

ISSUES OF IMPROVING LEGAL EDUCATION FOR YOUTH IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article provides a thorough scientific analysis of the current state of legal education for youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan, methods to enhance their legal knowledge and literacy, as well as the legal policies implemented in this area by the state.

Key words: Youth, youth policy, legal education, legal literacy, legal upbringing

Youth are the future of every society and play a significant role in the development of the state and ensuring socio-political stability. In Uzbekistan, improving the legal education of young people and raising them as legally cultured individuals is one of the urgent issues within the framework of youth policy. This article analyzes the legal foundations for improving legal education for young people, the measures being implemented, and the problems in this area.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of laws and regulations have been adopted to ensure the legal education of young people. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees the right to education, which serves as the main document for improving the legal literacy of young people. In addition, the "Law on State Policy Regarding Youth" and the "Law on Education" are aimed at ensuring comprehensive legal education for youth.

During a meeting on youth policy, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, proposed the creation of the Uzbekistan Children's Organization to develop children's skills, interests, and talents, and to provide them with

comprehensive support. It was noted that it is necessary to improve research and analytical work on studying youth problems and preparing promising personnel. Measures will be taken to increase the number of young people learning foreign languages to 1 million through the "Ibrat Farzandlari" project and the number of young readers to 1.5 million through the "Mutolaa" program. For this purpose, additional infrastructure will be built in regions to meaningfully organize young people's free time and create broader opportunities for realizing their talents and abilities.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to ensuring legal education and upbringing for youth in Uzbekistan. In particular, the "Uzbekistan Youth Union" established in 2017 upon the initiative of the country's leader has contributed significantly to the development of legal education for youth. Through the Youth Union, various seminars, training, and legal consultations are being organized to enhance the legal literacy of young people.

Today, improving the legal education of youth is one of the pressing issues, as it is crucial for the country's progress and the development of legal culture in society. Legal education aims to teach the younger generation to follow laws and instill legal knowledge and skills in them. The main goal of youth legal education is to educate young people about obeying laws and understanding their rights and obligations correctly. Additionally, through legal education, young people acquire the skills to protect their rights, defend themselves against various violations, and correctly understand the legal norms in society.

Main directions of legal education:

- Disseminating knowledge about legislation and providing young people with legal information.
- Organizing legal propaganda to prevent violations among youth.
- Developing active citizens by educating young people about their rights and responsibilities.

Several initiatives and projects are being implemented in Uzbekistan to

improve the legal literacy of youth:

1. Legal education in school and higher education systems: Legal subjects are being taught in schools to provide young people with legal knowledge. This helps instill respect for the law and provides the foundation of legal knowledge. In higher education institutions, legal subjects are also included in the mandatory curriculum.
2. Participation of external organizations and NGOs: Youth organizations and non-governmental organizations play a significant role in legal education for young people. They conduct training, seminars, and events aimed at improving legal literacy. In addition, legal consultation services for young people have been established.
3. Mass media: Through the mass media, legal knowledge is being promoted among young people. Television and radio programs on legislation are being broadcasted, enhancing legal awareness among the youth. Legal information is also widely disseminated on internet platforms.

Challenges and solutions There are several challenges in the field of legal education for youth, such as:

- Insufficient inclusion of legal subjects in school curricula.
- Limited legal subjects in higher education institutions.
- Inadequate coverage of legal information through mass media.

To address these challenges, the following measures can be taken:

- Strengthening the focus on legal subjects in school and higher education institutions.
- Expanding state programs aimed at improving legal literacy among youth.
- Increasing the dissemination of legal information through mass media and enhancing legal propaganda.
- Using television, radio, the internet, and other media to widely spread legal information among young people is crucial to popularizing legal education.

Various informational events can be organized to improve legal culture in society.

Conclusion Improving the legal education of youth in Uzbekistan is of great importance within the framework of state policy. Through legal education, young people become citizens who protect their rights, follow laws, and actively and responsibly participate in society. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in raising them as legally cultured and fair individuals in society.